

Port Harcourt Residents Perception and Response to Climate Change Reports in the News Media

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Abstract

This research is carried out in view of the many interests that have long tried to influence media reportage of climate change to affect the public's understanding, perception and response. The research method used is descriptive survey. Five objectives and five questions guided this study. The study focuses on Port Harcourt residents. The population consists of 1,865,000, and Taro Yamane's formula was used to select a sample of 400 respondents. A four point, Likert -type rating scale questionnaire titled: Port Harcourt Residents' Perception and Response to Climate Change Reports in the News Media was used to collect data from the respondents. The descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the demographic data while inferential statistic of Chi-square(x²) was used in testing the research hypotheses. Research findings showed that most residents perceived climate change as a result of deforestation, exhaust fume of vehicles and man-made activities and majority of the respondents agreed they are aware of climate change from the news media. The researcher therefore recommends that there should be useful climate information to effectively guide public debate and understanding about the weather and climate change. Policy makers should ensure regular and accurate communication about climate change and the media should ensure quality coverage of environmental issues.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is one of the most unsettled challenges facing the global community and as such has been given different definitions by different authors according to their perception and the way it affects them. Climate is generally defined as the weather condition prevailing in an area over a long period. The Intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC, 2007) defines climate change as any change in climate over time, whether due to natural variability or as a result of anthropogenic activities while, the United Nations, (1992) defines climate change as changes directly or indirectly caused by human activities over and above natural variation. History has shown that the environment is always changing, however, in the last 200 years, observations show that it is changing at a faster rate.

Reports by the Department of Ecology, the State of Washington (2017) shows that rising global Carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels and other heat-trapping gases in the atmosphere are warming the surface of the earth, resulting in rising sea levels, melting ice caps, flooding, droughts and wildfires. The increase in the concentration of these heat-trapping gases such as Methane (CH₄), Nitrous Oxide (NO₂), Carbon dioxide (CO₂) and Water Vapour (H₂O) by anthropogenic activities such as oil and gas exploration are a serious cause for concern. Of these gases, the effect of CO₂ emission stands out because it lasts much longer in the atmosphere.

Secondly, the overall amount of CH₄ and NO_x released by human activities are in small quantities when compared to CO₂ while H₂O persists only for a few days in the atmosphere.

Nigeria's climate has been changing, evident in: increases in temperature; variable rainfall; rise in sea level and flooding; drought and desertification; land degradation; more frequent extreme weather events; affected fresh water resources and loss of biodiversity Elisha et al. (2017); Ebele and Emodi (2016) and Olaniyi et al. (2013). The durations

and intensities of rainfall have increased, producing large runoffs and flooding in many places in Nigeria. Enete IC (2014). Rainfall variation is projected to continue to increase.

Precipitation in southern areas is expected to rise and rising sea levels are expected to exacerbate flooding and submersion of coastal lands Akande et al. (2017); Ebele and Emodi (2016). Droughts have also become a constant in Nigeria, and are expected to continue in Northern Nigeria, arising from a decline in precipitation and rise in temperature. Amanchukwu et al. (2015) and Olapido (2010). Lake Chad and other lakes in the country are drying up and at risk of disappearing. Dioha and Emodi (2018); Elisha et al. (2017).

Temperature has risen significantly since the 1980s Enete IC and Federal Ministry of Environment (2014). Climate projections for the coming decades reveal a significant increase in temperature over all the ecological zones Akande et al. (2017).

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change IPCC (2007), studies on the vulnerability of various sectors of the Nigerian economy to climate change reveal that climate change in due time will have great effect on human settlements, health, water resources, agriculture and food security. According to Umeji (2010) the issue of climate change cannot be shrugged off because its implications are legion especially on the African continent.

According to Abdulwali Yahaya (2019), Rivers State being the third highest oil producing state in Nigeria is also experiencing the effect of this global phenomenon. Port Harcourt is the centre of oil and gas activities in the state and has experienced its share of the impact of climate change. This is expected because the State hosts multinational oil and gas companies, banks and other financial institutions, manufacturing companies, construction and other allied services companies with significant energy consumption and high industrial emissions, which exacerbates the atmospheric pollution.

Climate change being a long-term and complex issue has a difficult position in the newsroom Farnsworth and Lichter, Bødker and Neverla, (2012). It has been on the agenda for over 30 years with no end in sight. Scientific discoveries regarding climate change are possibly made every day, yet most of the attention is directed towards international conferences and natural disasters Farnsworth and Lichter (2012). According to Bødker and Neverla, (2012) “apart from melting glaciers and extreme weather events, the issue of global warming is difficult to make concrete, and thus the subject of news”. US Journalist Ross Gelbspan, on the other hand, looks at it as a topic full of journalistic potential in the US, due to the conflict that has been generated by the Bush administration Gelbspan (2005). He sees US media lagging behind the rest of the (Western) world, failing to take up the topic of climate change. Even today, with the Bush administration long gone, Gelbspan attributes the US media a ‘stage-two’ denial of the climate crisis (2010), in other words, while the existence of climate change is now widely recognised, its urgency is still downplayed.

The media have an interest in reporting on issues that will result in high reader or viewership. It was mentioned that the personal conviction of a journalist might only have a marginal influence on his or her reporting, depending on the constraints by the economic and political interests of his or her employer. As Gelbspan points out, conflict is an important factor when it comes to creating public interest but all balance aside, there is also the simple depiction of climate change as a conspiracy, exaggeration or even as a positive development Boykoff (2008).

Looking back at the news values outlined above, this is not particularly surprising. Even when referring to the relatively conservative list by Galtung and Ruge, climate change, if looked at on a daily basis, would only fit values 5 (consonance) and 7 (continuity). However, it turns into a perfect news topic in the case of high-level international events and when extreme weather events happen, and this is reinforced by the updated set of news values. The UNFCCC conference in Copenhagen (COP15) in December 2009 caused an extremely high level of media coverage, as a feeling of urgency had been created in the weeks running up to the conference and a series of heads of states and governments, including the then US President Obama, attended the meeting.

Further coverage was fuelled by Climate gate, the publication of hacked emails by leading climate scientists who admitted to having exaggerated some aspects of their results Boykoff (2011). Media coverage of climate change has been, and remains, a significant factor in shaping public perceptions and attitudes toward the issue. Through time, mass media coverage has proven to be a key contributor among a number of factors that have shaped and affected science and policy discourse as well as public understanding and action. Media representational practices have broadly affected translations between science and policy and have shaped perceptions of various issues of environment, technology and risk Weingart et al. (2000).

The media have the responsibility of setting agenda and shaping the way the public understand certain issues like those of the science of climate change, its politics, its impact and the need for action. According to Mustapha (2012), the centrality of the mass media to the knowledge of goings-on in the society is at the heart of their influence on public’s

knowledge, attitudes and behaviour. To catch a glimpse of the happenings in the society or meet a psychic need, some read newspapers or magazine or both, while some others watch and listen to television and radio respectively.

In setting the agenda on climate change, the media can play a crucial role in disseminating useful climatic information to effectively guide public debate and understanding about the weather and climate change. Regular and accurate communication about climate change is the first step towards developing coping mechanisms in Africa Tagbo (2010).

There is an apparent important link between how the public perceive climate change and the impact of media coverage in Nigeria. A British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) research report (2008) draws attention to this linkage. The study asked what people in Nigeria thought about climate change and if communication and media strategies can be fashioned to aid Nigeria's response to climate change. Some of the findings of that study were as follows: Nigerians tended to believe strongly that they were personally and collectively responsible for local environmental and weather changes.

The Nigerian respondents were not aware that present and future climatic problems have causes beyond Nigeria. Nigerians use existing knowledge and beliefs to explain the effects of climate change. Religion plays some role in environmental management. People view climatic changes as acts of God while religious leaders call on people to protect God's creation. Opinion leaders, government, officials and non-governmental organisation representatives, social group leaders, religious leaders and traditional rulers are better informed about the global causes of climate change.

In the three major Nigerian languages; Igbo, Hausa, and Yoruba there is a lack of standard translation and understanding of climate change terminology. People in Nigeria mainly acquire information on climate change from the media and schools. However, there is a knowledge deficit in the media making audience education ineffective. Nigeria focuses mainly on mitigation strategies as opposed to adaptation programme. The knowledge of these facts is critical if the media and government are to take action which may bring solutions to the climate change problem.

The mass media play their basic role of information, education and entertainment in the society. This includes dissemination of information on green issues in the Nation and in the global scene. According to Nwabueze (2011) "when incidents with great significance to the environment and to the health of people take place in the society, the media expose such incident and make the public aware of them." Tagbo (2010), after a study, found that apart from being a disposable beat, climate change is a relatively new subject in many African media. Less than 30 percent of climate change journalists interviewed during the course of her study have reported the subject for more than three years of these, 60 percent identified a lack of training and time pressure as major reason why topic has rarely generated coverage commensurate to its significance for the comments future prosperity. Empirical data from Tagbo also shows that the Nigerian mass media have not been doing well in the coverage of environmental issues, with specific reference to climate change. After studying media images of environmental issues and problems in Nigeria, Nwosu and Uffoh (2005) discovered that the media give poor quality coverage to environmental issues.

Experts have emphasized the need to communicate effectively to policy makers about the future climate change so as to influence appropriate agricultural policies and adaptation strategies. The media, according to Tagbo (2010) can play a crucial role in disseminating useful climate information to effectively guide public debate and understanding about the weather and climate change. Tagbo (2010) also writes that regular and accurate communication about climate change is the first step towards developing coping mechanisms in Africa.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to examine Port Harcourt residents' perception and response to climate change reports in the news media. Precisely, the study sought to:

1. examine the perception of Port Harcourt residents' about climate change reports in the news media;
2. ascertain the response of Port Harcourt residents' towards climate change reports in the news media;
3. study the perception of Port Harcourt residents' towards climate change based on the level of their awareness on news media reports;

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the perception of Port Harcourt residents' about climate change reports in the news media?
2. What is the response of Port Harcourt residents' towards climate change reports in the news media?
3. What is the perception of Port Harcourt residents' towards climate change based on the level of their awareness on news media reports?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study on Port Harcourt residents' perception and response to climate change reports in the news media will be of immense importance to the residents, governmental and non-governmental agencies, policy makers, environmental management specialist, institutions and organisation, multinationals (oil and gas), religious institutions, media houses and environmental impact assessment institutions. This study will help these organisations know the effect of climate change so as to support, educate and create awareness to the residents on the possible influence it has on them. It is also significant to the residents in the sense that they will know the potential effects of climate change, so as to serve as watch-dog to those who are yet to know. This study will enable the government, media houses and every other bodies to be aware that climate change is a global event, exposing themselves more than necessary will pose unlikely dangers to their health. It will be appropriate in assisting residents in understanding the effect of climate change. It will provide relevant material for other researchers undertaking similar research. The study will help researchers with more information on resident's perception and response to climate change reports in the news media.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The spatial scope of this study was within the 20 wards in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. The scope of the study in terms of content was to assess residents perception and response to climate change reports in the news media. The targeted populations are the residents of Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. The temporal scope of the research is based on resident's perception and response to climate change reports in the news media and number of years the respondents who constituted the sample indicated a change in climatic conditions during their stay in Port Harcourt. The major research variables include climate change, residents' perception and response.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Beside time and cost constraints, there are other limitations in this study. They include: data distribution and collection process which was due to the size of the area to be investigated as well as the large population of the residents in Port Harcourt. There was also the constraint of credible response as most of the residents were shy and therefore reluctant to respond truthfully. These limitations however, did not compromise the quality of this study as adequate measures were taken to this effect.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Media Framing Theory

Media framing theory was propounded by Erving Guffman in (1974). He referred to it as framing analysis. However, it was Robert Entman who gave it a media outlook. An important proposition of media framing theory is that communication text in news report bears resemblance with and could share a common wave length of reasoning between the intension of the sender of the message and the mental disposition of the receiver. In other words there is never an unframed message if it is a message at all. Thus, in the variables of message intent enunciated by Entman (1993), a message frame always involves ingredients of salience purposively or surreptitiously; meaning, it attracts attention to something by amplifying what it draws attention to.

According to Entman (1993), media framing essentially involves selection and salience. To frame is to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation for the item described. The term salience, according to Entman (1993) means: "making a piece of information more noticeable, meaningful, or memorable to audience". An increase in salience improves the probability that the audience will remember the information. Thus, Freyenberger (2013) notes that information can be added or taken out according to the message that media want to communicate to the public. The theory projects framing as a perceptual activity endorsed to carry out four functions as Entman (2008), submits namely: define problems, specify causes, convey moral assessments, and endorse remedies.

The way individuals classify information also adds to the framing theory and framing is both a macro and a micro level construct Scheufele and Tewksbury, (2007). As a macro construct, the term framing refers to modes of presentation that journalists and other communicators use to present information in a way that resonates with existing underlying schemas among their audience. Micro construct explains how individuals use the information they receive to form impressions about the issue. Each of these variables contributes to the public's view of certain issues. Media have the power to generate a specific reaction from the public by the way the story is portrayed. The way in which news events are covered by the media can affect how receivers of that news come to understand the events. Recipients of a news story build their opinion based on how the news story was framed and their own individual frames.

Viewers interpret and process information based on the tone of the news story. Scheufele (1999). A single sentence may perform more than one of these four framing functions, although many sentences in a text may perform none of

them. And a frame in any particular text may not necessarily include all four functions. Texts can make bits of information more salient by placement or repetition, or by associating them with culturally familiar symbols. Framing influence over these sentiments can be characterized more precisely by employing the following formula according to Entman (2008):

Attitude = $\sum viwi$, where

V_i is the evaluation of the object on attribute i

And w_i is the salience weight ($\sum w_i=1$) associated with that attribute.

It is the idea of Entman (2008) that, framing influences and alter audience member's interpretations and preferences through priming. To effectively do that frames must draw potency for the moment from congruent elements of schemas or identifiable structures that represent knowledge about a concept or type of stimulus probably stored in the past. Schemas fit new perceptions to an existing organization of knowledge. So media frames are organizing devices that help journalists and the public make sense of issues and thus inject them with meaning, while generating bias at the same time Hannigan (1995). It operates by biasing the cognitive processing of information by individual Hallahan (1999). Entman (1993) notes that people's prior knowledge, allows them to make sense of new information by deciding consciously or not how the new material fits into their understandings and feelings about the world.

Most frames are defined by what they omit as well as include, and the omissions of potential problem definitions, explanations, evaluations, and recommendations may be as critical as the inclusions in guiding the audience. It is important to acknowledge that media framing essentially involves two aspects: news selection and news description. Earl, Martin, McCarthy, and Soule (2004). Firstly, since a large number of potential issues compete with each other for highly limited attention Carmines and Stimson (1993), not all the news will be considered as newsworthy; and the sample of issues appearing in newspapers is not always representative.

Ader's (1995) study, for example, illustrates that real world conditions do not influence the media agenda directly. In other words, what determine newsworthiness are not the objective characteristics of issues. Rather, it is structured by various factors such as competition over newspaper space, reporting norms and editorial concerns Earl, Martin, McCarthy and Soule (2004). Secondly, description bias concerns the veracity with which selected events are reported in the press Earl, Martin, McCarthy and Soule (2004). Researchers have identified five devices: metaphors, exemplars, catchphrases, depictions and visual images, and three reasoning devices: roots (causal analysis), consequences and appeals to principle. Gamson and Modigliani (1989). Each one can be used to transfer salience.

Framing is the act of highlighting certain aspects of a story to allow for interpretation and context, thus making an event or story more understandable for the audience Entman (2004) and McQuail (2005). Put simply, framing is an act of defining issues typically by elites for public consumption, and disseminating these definitions through the use of mass media. Tucker (1998), wrote that frames are highly ritualized symbolic structures embedded into media content. These frames, as part of the media structure and content, control the flow of information to the audience. Tuchman (1978) equates the framing process to looking through a window.

Tuchman cited by McCann (2010) stated: The view through a window depends upon whether the window is large or small, has many panes or few, whether the glass is opaque or clear, whether the window faces a street or backyard. The unfolding scene also depends upon where one stands, far or near, craning one's neck to the side, or gazing straight ahead, eyes parallel to the wall in which the window is encased. The window metaphor provides a clear example of how the news frame can include, exclude and skew specific pieces of information depending on what information is placed within view or outside of the metaphorical window.

Framing research emerging from sociological foundations focuses, according to Borah (2011) on the phrases, words and images that are used to construct news stories. Several empirical work and researches Antilla (2005); Boykoff (2007); Boykoff and Boykoff (2007); Carvalho (2007); Doulton and Brown (2007) have found, variously, the use of frames by the media in presenting the issue of climate change to the public in the Western countries. This may not be different from the developing nations. Nisbet, (2009) reasons that frames are: so many things to so many people. For example audiences rely on frames to make sense of and discuss an issue; journalists use frames to craft interesting and appealing news reports; policymakers apply frames to define policy options and reach decisions and experts employ frames to simplify technical details and make them persuasive. Frames are interpretive storylines that set a specific train of thought in motion, communicating why an issue might be a problem, who or what might be responsible for it and what should be done about it.

Inducing people to rationalize and behave according to Entman (2008), in consonance requires elites to select certain things to inform them and what to spare them of and similarly embedding cues on how this narratives coheres with their schemata or prior attitudes and values. Some scholars are given to think that framing may just be the same as other bias

theories like agenda setting and priming. While it may be difficult to dismiss altogether, because there are relationships between framing theory and priming for example; there are fine lines of differences per se.

Entman (2008) issuing from political communication stand point however differs to the assumption that framing is a nomenclatural change to bias theories like agenda setting and framing. The confusion is generated essentially by refusing or glossing over the difference between bias and slant, or interposing one for the other in journalistic practice and text. Slant is introduced in a report when a report helms in and bloats (frames), a perspective in a political conflict while ignoring or obliterating or derogating another sides. This operation emphasizes some elements and suppresses others in ways that encourage recipients to give attention and weight to the evaluative attributes (vi and wi) that privilege the favored sides interpretation. This is the essence of slanted news. Indeed, slanted framing is also the primary mechanism through which interpersonal communication leverages political power, in conversations, speeches and negotiations. In spite of journalistic difference to slanted news through normative like objectivity, slanted news remains a particularly strong habit that die hard as Cunningham (2003); Boykoff (2007) and Nisbet (2009) claim.

On the other hand, media content bias can only be realistic when empirical study establishes a perpetual slant of information to suit an interest over time, particularly where there is plurality of that phenomenon in other media organizations studied similarly. The other variable in understanding media bias according to Entman (2008) concerns decision making bias. Why are certain stories reported, emphasized, glossed over etc., are functions of, largely, personal ideologies of journalists and editors. Sometimes these are not so apparent because they hide under institutionalized media norms and routines like objectivity, balance and fairness. One way that media framing has been studied is by viewing the theory as a process.

De Vreese (2005) examined the communicative processes of framing thus: Communication is not static but rather a dynamic process that includes frame building and frame setting. Frame building would refer to the elements that influence the structure of each news frame internally. However, external variables are also important in the equation. Hence, the frame building process takes place in a continuous interaction between journalists, elites and social movements De Vreese (2005). This process is expressed in the text of the news story. Frame setting refers to the interaction between media frames and individual's prior knowledge and pre-dispositions. There are consequences of framing on the individual and the societal level. An individual level consequence maybe altered attitudes about an issues based on exposure to certain frames. On the societal level, frames may contribute to shaping social level processes such as political socialization, decision making and collective actions. Framing can affect the individual and public knowledge of a news topic.

Semetko and Valkenburg's (2000) research involving national news coverage found that the media's most common frames, in order of predominance were attribution of responsibility, conflict, economic consequences, human interest and morality. However, Brunken (2006) notes that such findings may not be consistent and all-encompassing in the case of a natural disaster and environmental issues. Media's use of these frames package meaning into organized ideas, allowing them to shape the way they tell the story. Iyengar's (1991) research contends that news about political issues takes either an episodic or thematic frame stating that, the episodic news frame focuses on specific events or particular cases, while the thematic news frame places political issues and events in some general context. In the light of this, environmental issue is not a general news event; giving that the extraordinary circumstances involved, like massive flooding and a large death toll, makes it a specific news event.

Ghanem (1997) breaks down frames into four dimensions: topic, presentation, affective attributes, and cognitive attributes. Attributes are subtopics of the object or issue being presented. Topics, like frames, create issue salience in news reporting. Placement and size are influential elements of framing. The way in which topics are presented, including placement of an article in a newspaper and size of the article, influences opinion of the topic being discussed. A third dimension to framing is affective, which involves the public's emotional response that may result from media coverage Ghanem (1997). Schudson (1982) argues that the power of the media lies in the forms in which declarations appear. Therefore, as storytellers the media have the power to order news using the inverted pyramid style, thereby engaging the public sooner and extending their interest. Print media sometimes display personal stories, locally and nationally, of family members literally washed away by storm surges and killed by rising water.

As such, bringing a story to such a personal level might help the reader identify with the happenings in the story and thus make the reader feel more concern for what is going on. Ghanem,(1997). This is akin to Dahinden (2002) identification. Dahinden (2002) identified the four levels of framing as: media content, production, audience frames and general culture. Media content refers to story selection and patterns of reporting. Production refers to how content is presented, including journalistic norms. Audiences frames take into account the existing mental models and schemas activated by media. Culture refers to the existing narratives and myths found in modern society Dahinden (2005).

However, in analyzing the postulation of framing theory Brunken (2006) attest that Entman (1993) argues that frames have at least four locations in the communication process: the communicator, the text, the receiver and the culture. Firstly, communicators consciously or unconsciously make frame-guided judgments that organize their belief systems. Meaning that the first location has to do with the content of frames and their amalgamation of textual items (words and images) with the contextual treatment that they receive from framing devices. D'Angleo (2002). The second location, the text, contains frames which are manifested by the presence or absence of certain key words, stock phrases, stereotyped images, sources of information and sentences that provide thematically reinforcing clusters of facts or judgments. Entman (1993). Kinder and Sanders (1990) suggest, in the third location, that frames lead a double life as internal structures of the mind and devices embedded in political discourse. Individuals, or receivers, use frames as prior knowledge to efficiently process information.

These processed frames are part of the commonly invoked frames of a larger culture, the fourth location. The culture is the supply of commonly used frames displayed in social discourse and thinking. Thus, framing in all four locations includes similar functions: selection and highlighting, and use of the highlighted elements to construct an argument about problems and their causation, evaluation, and/or solution Entman 1993. Schramm and Roberts (1971) wrote that all aspects of a story from length, size of the headline, position on the page, page of print, inclusion of a picture, caption of the picture, and author's byline all convey the level of importance of the news item to the reader. Graber (1984, 2002) noted that the visual presentation of news stories headlines, pictures, and page placement contribute to the overall salience.

Verbiage is an important part of the framing process. Once certain terms become accepted, the language itself has power over audience interpretations. The use of certain words or phrases McQuail (2005) can be used to convey specific meanings. Verbiage is so integral to framing that straying from commonly accepted terms might result in a loss of understanding. Entman (1993) wrote: Once a term is widely accepted, to use another is to risk that target audiences will perceive the communicator as lacking credibility or will even fail to understand what the communicator is talking about. Thus the power of a frame can be as great as that of language itself.

The media play a crucial role in reinforcing verbiage as it relates to a problem or an issue. Carvalho (2005) noted that the media are a crucial site for the definition and re-definition of meanings associated with climate change. The ability of the public to understand environmental issues depends largely upon how such issues are constructed by media verbiage, and without public understanding there can be no public debate or resolution Carvalho (2005).

Agenda-Setting Theory

Agenda-setting theory was propounded by Maxwell McCombs and Donald L. Shaw in the year 1972/1973. Agenda-setting theory is concerned with the potency of media's power to influence public member's thoughts of subject matter they adjudged worthy of particular attention. Its proposition is that the media have the power to direct and redirect people's thought on what to focus on. The mass media, according to the theory enunciated by McCombs and Shaw (1972) set the tempo of discussion and let the pressure deflate to an angle which eventually becomes the estuary of attention or the salience in the debate. It is the media that set the echo point of discussions in society, or as McCombs and Shaw (1972) quotes Cohen to have noted that the press may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but it is stunningly successful in telling its readers what to think about. In a review of agenda setting research, McCombs and Shaw (1993) suggest that Cohen's argument has been turned inside out. New research suggests that the media not only tell us what to think about, but also how to think about it, and, consequently, what to think.

They gave perspective to the theory by articulating the following thoughts on the theory according to Baran and Davis (2006). In choosing and displaying news, editors, newsroom staff and broadcasters play an important part in shaping political reality. Readers learn not only about a given issue, but how much importance to attach to that issue from the amount of information in a news story and its position. The mass media may well determine the important issues; that is the media may set the agenda of the campaign. The core principle of agenda setting theory is that the prominence of elements in the news influences the prominence of those elements among the public. Carol and McCombs (2003).

There are two levels of agenda setting. The first level is concerned with the salience of objects (public issues, public figures, or companies) and the second level is concerned with the salience of the characteristics of those objects. Carol and McCombs (2003). This second level agenda setting includes, according to Brunken (2006), attribute-agenda setting and framing. Thus, Attribute agenda setting suggests a more subtle form of media effect than agenda setting, focusing not on coverage of objects, but on how the media cover attributes of those objects Craft and Wanta (2003). Attributes are the set of perspectives or frames that journalists and the public employ to think about each object Ghanem (1997).

While traditional agenda setting research mainly involved amount of news coverage, attribute agenda setting research examines the tone of news coverage. Hester and Gibson (2003). Second level agenda setting hypothesizes that both the selection of topics for attention and the selection of attributes for thinking about these topics play powerful agenda-

setting roles. Hester and Gibson (2003). Attribute agenda setting occurs when media use topics or attributes of an issue or event to deliver news. Topics and attributes may be considered one and the same, as both act as pieces and parts that contribute to understanding an event or issue in its entirety.

Ghanem (1997) suggests that, “The frequency with which a topic is mentioned probably has a more powerful influence than any particular framing mechanism (a focal point of news presentation), but framing mechanisms could serve as catalysts to frequency in terms of agenda setting.” That means, while repeatedly mentioned topics may influence public opinion, emphasis or elaboration of these repeated topics may prove even more influential. Hester and Gibson (2003) address the use of tone as an element of attribute agenda setting. Traditionally, it is understood that media mirror public opinion and monitor change, not purposefully influencing public opinion. Hester and Gibson (2003). However, traditional notions of news also suggest that the bulk of media coverage will be negative.

Hester and Gibson (2003) suggest that the media are often charged with overemphasizing negative news and downplaying positive news. The idea of negative news is not necessarily always about unfavorable angle of an issue. A negative tone in news presentation could also be implied when news substance is skewed to framing a problem in the news element of “what” happened each time a story is reported. Repeated attention paid to a story can determine how powerful an influence it will have on the public. McCombs (1997) described agenda setting as the transmission of salience, not the determination of opinions pro and con about a particular issue. He explained that news media do not intentionally or deliberately set the agenda for the newscast. Nevertheless, the topics that are chosen to be the main focus in a news story can affect the opinions of the audience.

According to McCombs (1997) there are four visions of agenda-setting that should be identified. These four visions describe both what the agenda-setting role of the news media is and the professional views of journalists about what the agenda-setting role of the news media should be. He called the first vision professional detachment. The vision states that the main focus of a journalist is to only report the news and to stand apart from the public. McCombs reasons that vision interrogates the perception of agenda-setting because more often than not the news media are incapable of standing apart from the community. Whatever the media do, they have an effect on the community they serve. News media may attempt objective report of the news, but then the community will still be interested and feel the effects of how the news was portrayed to them.

The second vision of agenda-setting is called targeted involvement. This vision gravitates toward the active end of the agenda-setting scale in that investigative reporting and editorial campaigns actively seek to move issues unto the public agenda and vis-à-vis a considerable portion of the government’s agenda, where specific subject is for example enunciated. This agenda-setting vision attempts to set the community’s agenda as well as the government’s agenda. The next vision is called boosterism. McCombs (1997) explained that this type of news coverage could seem like cheerleading. Economic development in a community, everything from the new jobs that can result from a business firm coming to the community to the expenditure of public funds for construction of roads and community facilities, is news worthy up to a point.

However, at a certain point there should be a line drawn between publicity and newsworthy information as Freyberger (2013) submits. The final vision of agenda-setting is called proactive agenda-setting. McCombs argues that, journalists believe that it is the duty and responsibility of the news media to ensure, through proactive reporting (when necessary, that the key issues); situations, and opportunities do come to community attention. He insists by stating that journalists are privileged and that the core assumption of public journalism and proactive agenda-setting is that this privilege should be actively used to benefit the public.”

The elements or indicators involved in the theory as Folarin (1998) and Anaeto, Onabajo and Osifeso (2008) note are:

1. The quantity or frequency of reporting,
2. Prominence given to the reports through headlines display, pictures and layout in newspapers, magazines, film, graphics or timing on radio and television,
3. The degree of conflict generated in the reports and
4. Cumulative media specific effects over time.

Nevertheless, some scholars like Wilson (1996) and McQuail (2000) both quoted by Harcup (2009) dismiss agenda-setting as, at best a hackneyed half-truth on grounds that it downplays the existence of multiple agendas and that it remains a plausible but unproven idea respectively. Baran and Davis (2012) contend that it is important not to judge the utility of the agenda-setting approach based on the earliest studies. Although these had many limitations, they have inspired some other research that is providing intriguing if still controversial results. A step beyond the initial thought has birth priming and agenda building. The former, priming is, as Baran and Davis (2006) note, drawing attention to some aspects of political life at the expense of others; the latter, agenda-building, is seen as a collective process in which media, government and the citizenry reciprocally influence one another, as Lang and Lang (1983) quoted by Baran and Davis (2006) affirm.

Research studies into agenda-setting take two forms as Watson (2003) notes: hierarchy studies survey all the issues on the media agenda at a given time; longitudinal studies investigate fewer issues, possibly two or three, tracing their rise and fall over a period of time. Watson notes that longitudinal studies tend to counter the notion that events spring dramatically from the media to the public agenda. Working through the cumulative effect of media messages about an issue, functionalized through the relentless and accumulated impact of a repeated message topic, slowly, the public agenda for an issue builds up. Dearing and Rogers (1996) quoted by Watson (2003) reason that how an issue is reported is as important as whether the issue is reported at all and this may gain momentum through what they refer to as triggers, that is, particular incidents, or personal involvements by usually well-known people that are issue champions.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is descriptive survey. This design was considered appropriate because it enables the researcher generate data through the standardized collection procedures based on highly structured research instrument(s) and well defined study concepts and related variables.

Population of the Study

The study comprises of Port Harcourt residents. Based on the data obtained from the National Population Commission Census of 2006, projected by 2.5% till 2019, Port Harcourt's total population is 1,865,000. Port Harcourt residents were chosen because it has potentials that encourage investment. There are mineral resources that are available to be explored or used for commercial purposes.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size of 400 was drawn from a population of 1,865,000 using Taro Yamane formula calculation. This consists of residents drawn from Port Harcourt. The simple random sampling technique use in selecting the residents is to ensure that every person have an equal opportunity of being selected.

Research Instrument

A well-constructed self-developed questionnaire titled Port Harcourt residents perception and response to climate change reports in the news media was administered in two sections; A – Personal data collection and B – the response pattern was structured in line with the modified four point Likert scale of:

Strongly agree (4 points)
 Agree (3 points)
 Disagree (2 points)
 Strongly disagree (1 point)

There are thirty nine (39) items in the questionnaire and it was organised in four sections. Section A, B, C D. Section A was on demographic data while Sections B to D focused on the research questions. Questions 1-7 answer the question to research section A. Questions 8-16 answer the question to research section B, questions 17-26 answer the question to research section C, and questions 27-39 answer the question to research section D.

Validity of the Instrument

Based on the suggestion of the supervisor, the instrument was restructured to ensure that it was able to measure the variables it was supposed to measure.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the study instrument was determined through the use of test-re test method. The person Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. A co-efficient of 0.65 indicated that the research instrument was reliable hence; it is adopted for getting the desired information for this study.

Source of Data

The researcher collected the needed data through the use of questionnaire and its administration in the selected area. The administration of the questionnaire was carried out by the researcher. A total of 400 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to elicit responses from the residents and retrieved either on the spot and a week later by the researcher. A total of 5 questionnaires were missing while 12 were wrongly filled leaving the researcher with 383 valid questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using frequency table and Percentages while the inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

What is the perception of Port Harcourt residents towards climate change on news media in Rivers State?

According to Godfrey, Le Roux-Rutledge, Cooke and Burton (2009) states that most people in Nigeria, Port Harcourt to be precise considers climate change to be an abstract, despite their understanding of changing weather patterns. Also, access to information is critical in shaping the public level of climate change awareness. However, Saroar and Routray (2010) agreed that access to information determines individual's knowledge of climate change, which eventually influences behaviour. People who either read newspapers or other related prints, listen to radios, watch televisions or have access to the internet are more likely to be familiar with climate change than those who do not have access to such media information. Basically, the study on the influence of media coverage on Japanese public awareness of climate change issues conducted by Sampei and Aoyagi-Usui (2009) opines that intense newspaper coverage on global warming issues is associated with an increase in public concern over climate change.

What is the response of Port Harcourt residents towards climate change on news media in Rivers State?

Majority of the respondents believe that climate change is caused by deforestation, exhaust fume of vehicles, excessive release of carbon dioxide, industrial effluents, rapid urbanization, changes in people's lifestyle, increase in population growth and man's activities.

According to a longitudinal survey on Americans conducted between the years 2008 and 2011 by Myers, Maibach, Roser-Renouf, Akerlof and Leiserowitz (2013) discovered respectively that experience of the impacts of climate change provides the opportunity for experiential learning especially among people who are less engaged in climate change issues. It is only through experience of the impacts of climate change that lay people become more certain that climate change is happening and they need to do something in order to increase their level of resilience. It is believed that the media has done well in disseminating news on climate change in the news media in Rivers State.

What is the perception of Port Harcourt residents based on level of awareness about climate change on news media in Rivers State?

Majority of the respondents accepts they have health challenges because of climate change, there is decrease in crop production, climate change makes lives unbearable for residents, they prepare for heavy rainfall and flooding but however, some respondents rejects that climate change affect the standard of living.

According to Pew Research Centre Global Attitudes Project survey conducted in 2006, people from developed countries are increasingly aware of climate change compared to those in developing countries. Similar findings were revealed by Gallup's global opinion poll conducted between 2008 and 2009 in 128 countries around the world, which shows that people in Europe and America are more aware of climate change than those in Africa, Asia and Middle East regions (Pugliese and Ray, 2009).

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, the following conclusion were made; the media have the responsibility of setting agenda and shaping the way the public understand certain issues like those of the science of climate change, its politics, its impact and the need for action. To catch a glimpse of the happenings in the society or meet a psychic need, some read newspapers or magazine or both, while some others watch and listen to television and radio respectively. Most residents believe that climate change is caused by man's activities and climate change leads to change of pattern of rainfall. Majority of the respondents believe that climate change makes life unbearable and that it affects the standard of living. The residents believe that setting the agenda on climate change on media could play a crucial role in disseminating useful climatic information to effectively guide public debate and understanding about the weather and climate change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The media should ensure quality coverage to environmental issues. Reports on environmental issues should explore the reigns of situating the environmental issues they cover in a bigger interpretative picture of climate change/global warming that seems to have answers to causes of the environmental issues in society and how to mitigate the problems.
2. Climate change information should not be presented as hard, complex scientific information. Topics should emphasize human interest.
3. Policy makers should ensure regular and accurate communication about climate change. Government can as well direct people through TV programmes, radio and the internet to read and listen to news about climate change information.
4. There should be useful climate information to effectively guide public debate and understanding about the weather and climate change.

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